

Data for Policy 2022

Ecosystems of innovation and
virtual-physical interactions

5 December - Hong Kong

8/9 December – Seattle

13 December - Brussels

Data for Policy 2022

Ecosystems of innovation and virtual-physical interactions

#dataforpolicy2022

Seattle Programme

9th December, Seattle time

Hybrid – In-person and online (UW Parrington Hall and Zoom)

*denotes presenting author

†denotes virtual presentation

09:30 – 10:50 **Arrival and refreshments**

9:50 – 10:10 **Welcome and Land Acknowledgment**

Leigh **Anderson** (Marc Lindenberg Professor of Humanitarian Relief, International Development & Global Citizenship)

The University of Washington acknowledges the Coast Salish peoples of this land, the land which touches the shared waters of all tribes and bands within the Duwamish, Puyallup, Suquamish, Tulalip and Muckleshoot nations.

Master of Ceremonies:

AM Shaida **Badiee** (Managing Director, Open Data Watch) and Zeynep **Engin** (Open Infrastructure Strategy Lead, and AI for Science and Government Theme Lead for Tools, Practices & Systems, Alan Turing Institute)

PM Stefaan **Verhulst** (Co-Founder and Chief Research and Development Officer and Director of GovLab's Data Program)

Opening Remarks

Greg **Wong** (Deputy Mayor of Seattle) and Jodi **Sandfort** (University of Washington)†

10:10 – 11:00 **Plenary Panel 'Local Data and Policy'**

Panel Moderator: Leah Tivoli (Director of Innovation & Performance, City of Seattle)

Panelists:

Natalia **Carfi** (Executive Director, Open Data Charter, Buenos Aires, Argentina)

Eva **Westley** (Associate Director of Research, Washington State Institute for Public Policy)

Greg **Wong** (Deputy Mayor, Seattle, Washington)

11:00 – 11:45 Session 1 ‘Data and Methods to Inform Covid Lessons’

Moderator: Stefaan **Verhulst** (Co-Founder and Chief Research and Development Officer and Director of GovLab's Data Program)

[7473] Wilson **Wong*** (The Chinese University of Hong Kong), Charles **Hinnant** (Florida State University), Lin **Zhu** (National University of Singapore) and Alfred **Wu** (National University of Singapore). Trust-Enabled Data Technology in Smart City: *Comparing the COVID-19 Contact Tracing App of Hong Kong and Singapore.*

[7582] Zahra Movahedi **Nia*** (York University), Ali **Asgary** (York University), Nicola **Bragazzi** (York University), Bruce **Mellado** (University of Witwatersrand), James **Orbinski**, Jianhong **Wu** and Jude Kong (York University). *Tracing Unemployment Rate of South Africa during the COVID-19 Pandemic Using Twitter Data.*

[5066] Vahid **Shamsaddini** (Sharif University of Technology), Mandy **Chen** (University of Washington), Fiona Victoria Stanley **Jothiraj*** (University of Washington) and Afra **Mashhadi** (University of Washington). *Empirical Dynamic Modelling of the Multi-Source Park Visitation Data*

11:45 – 12:00 Short break and refreshments

12:00 – 12:50 Keynote Lecture

Speaker Introduction: Ashley **Farley** (Associate Officer, Knowledge & Research Services, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation)

Speaker: Professor Carl **Bergstrom** (University of Washington) *Social media, Collective Decision-making, and the stewardship of Global Information Flows*

12:50 – 13:50 Lunch and networking

Data for Policy Inclusion Initiative: Diasmer Panna **Bloe**

13:50 – 14:40 Plenary Panel ‘Indigenous Data’

Panel Moderator: Laura **Evans** (Evans School of Public Policy and Governance, University of Washington)

Panelists:

Aaron **Franks** (Senior Research Manager, OCAP® and Information Governance, First Nations Information Governance Centre, Ottawa)

Oscar **Figueroa Rodriguez**† (Associate Professor, Rural Development Studies Program, COLPOS, Mexico)

Kayla **Lar-Son** (Indigenous Programs and Services Librarian, University of British Columbia)

Miranda **Belarde-Lewis** (Assistant Professor, UW Information School)

14:40 – 15:30 Session 2 Standard Track 2 (Data Technologies and Analytics for Policy and Governance) Panel ‘Towards an Inclusive Data Governance Policy for the use of AI in Africa’

Moderator: Chaitali **Sinha**† (International Development Research Centre, Canada)

[3891] Jude **Kong*** (York University), Ugochukwu **Akpudo**† (Griffith University QLD Australia), Jake Okechukwu **Effoduh**, and Nicola Luigi **Bragazzi** (York University) *Leveraging ‘Responsible, Explainable, and Local Artificial Intelligence Solutions for Clinical Public Health in the Global South’ (REL-AI4GS): Implications for Policies and Lessons Learned from the ‘Africa-Canada Artificial Intelligence and Data Innovation Consortium’ (ACADIC) project*

[3891] Jake Okechukwu **Effoduh*** (York University), Ugochukwu **Akpudo**† (Griffith University QLD Australia) and Jude **Kong** (York University) *Designing Data Governance Policies for the Inclusive use of Artificial Intelligence in Africa*

[3891] Ugochukwu **Akpudo***† (Griffith University QLD Australia), Jake Okechukwu **Effoduh** and Jude **Kong** (York University) *AI and vulnerabilities in sub-Saharan Africa: The need for trustworthiness, reliability and equitable access*

15:30 – 15:45 Short break and refreshments

15:45 – 16:35 Session 3 ‘Citizen Data and Data Governance’

Moderator: Ashley **Farley** (Associate Officer, Knowledge & Research Services, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation)

[8028] Valeria Maria **Urbano*** (Politecnico di Milano), Federico **Bartolomucci** (Politecnico di Milano) and Giovanni **Azzone** (Politecnico di Milano). *Determinants for citizens’ location data sharing with public institutions during a pandemic: the Italian case .*

[8350] Zena **Wood***† (University of Exeter) and Glen **Hart** (DSTL). *Data Reuse: comparing the principles.*

[3945] Trishi **Jindal*** (NLSIU Bangalore) and Srijoni **Sen** (NLSIU Bangalore). *What's a Record got to do with it?: Re-situating records management within Indian public data governance and policy.*

[4616] Olumurejiwa **Fatunde*** (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) and Patrick **Brock** (UNHCR). *Using automated text analysis to understand downstream usage of UNHCR operational data.*

16:35 – 17:25 Standard Track 6 (Data to Tackle Global Issues and Dynamic Societal Threats)
Panel 'Leveraging Data to Set Objectives and Make Decision: What Can We Learn from Impact Assessments? The Experience from IFAD'

Panel Moderator: Richard **Caldwell** (Senior Program Officer, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation)

Panelists:

Athur **Mabiso*** (International Fund for Agricultural Development). *Going from Project to Corporate Level Impact Assessments. IFAD's Experience* [standing in for Sara Savastano]

Athur **Mabiso*** (International Fund for Agricultural Development). *Investing in Value Chain for Rural Transformation*

Carlo **Azzarri***† (International Food Policy Research Institute). *Women's Empowerment for Rural Transformation*

Sinafikeh **Gemessa*** (International Fund for Agricultural Development). *Investing towards Sustainable Carbon Neutral Livestock Development*

17:25 Closing Remarks

Stefaan **Verhulst**

17:30 - 18:30 Networking reception

With thanks to our partner organisations
